

Educational Approaches to Advancing Environmental Literacy: A Review of NEP 2020

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Abstract

Environmental literacy must be possessed by every human being, to effectively address the serious global environmental issues. The need of environmental literacy in solving today's environmental challenges is becoming more widely understood. National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 in India stresses the need to integrate sustainability and environmental consciousness throughout the educational curriculum, from primary education to higher learning. This study reviews NEP2020's framework for promoting and integrating environmental literacy into education system and analyzing its impact on students, teachers and communities. It focuses into the goals and strategies of NEP2020 on how it intends to incorporate environment literacy into the educational curriculum. Preliminary results suggest that NEP 2020 could help cultivate a new generation of environmentally aware citizens. The study also underscores how the policy aligns with global educational trends that prioritize sustainability and a comprehensive understanding of environmental challenges. The paper highlights the conceptual model of environmental literacy. The initial findings indicate that NEP 2020 has the potential to cultivate environmentally conscious citizens while aligning with global standards of excellence. The paper suggests some educational strategies for promoting the environment related sliteracy at school, higher educational institutions and teacher training institutions. The study further highlights the effective execution of NEP 2020 and suggests the teachers and administration to successfully execute the environment literacy in the education system.

Key words: Environmental Literacy, NEP2020, Education, Curriculum.

Introduction:

Environmental literacy relates to the knowledge, abilities, skills, and attitudes that enable individuals to understand and address environmental related issues. There are five qualities of environmental literacy as proposed by UNESCO in 1977 are discussed as follows:

1. Being aware of and sensitive to the environment in its entirety
2. Gaining knowledge and practical experience related to environmental challenges
3. Developing values and emotional connections to the natural world
4. Acquiring the skills needed to identify and address environmental problems
5. Building the ability and motivation to actively participate in solving environmental issues at all levels

Environmental literacy is the key outcome of environmental education. It enables individuals to understand the interrelationships between people, societies, and natural systems, and how these interactions can be managed sustainably. To make informed decisions about consumption, lifestyle, career, and civic engagement, individuals must possess a solid foundation of environmental awareness, knowledge, skills, and attitudes.

Environmental literacy supports several United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly Goal 4 (Quality Education), Goal 13 (Climate Action), and Goal 15 (Life on Land). SDG 4

seeks to provide inclusive, equitable, and high-quality education, along with lifelong learning opportunities for all, as part of the broader 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development.

Environmental literacy promotes critical thinking and enhances problem-solving abilities, scientific comprehension, data analysis and interpretation, systems thinking, civic and ethical responsibility, communication skills, action and advocacy, sustainable practices, interdisciplinary integration, and personal and social awareness amongst the learners. In India root of modern environmental education is traced in 1937 with the concept of Mahatma Gandhi's concept that relates to "basic education" which focuses on learning by doing. The National Policy on Education 1968 did not recognize environmental studies as a distinct subject. It was only with the N C F of 1975 that environmental concerns began to receive some attention. The NPE 1986 laid a stronger foundation for correlating environmental education into the curriculum. In 1991, the Supreme Court mandated the inclusion of environmental education as a compulsory subject across all levels, from schools to universities. However, the environmental education curriculum has largely focused on theoretical knowledge, often overlooking the development of skills, values, attitudes, and experiential knowledge. The (NEP) 2020, India's first education policy of the 21st century, brings a transformative shift by promoting a holistic, flexible, and multidisciplinary approach. "It places a strong importance on vocational training and the advancement of environmental literacy, while aligning closely with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals and the 2030 Agenda." The National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 seeks to promote sustainable practices and environmental awareness from a young age. It places significant focus on incorporating environmental education into curricula at all educational levels, ranging from schools to higher education institutions.

This integration promotes environmental awareness and aids in conservation and sustainable development. Teacher training educational programmes will also include environmental related curriculum. Higher education institutions are encouraged to offer credit-based courses and projects centered on community engagement and service connected to environmental education. "The (NEP) 2020 underscores the vital importance of embedding environmental education as a central element of academic curricula. It advocates for fostering environmental awareness and sensitivity, with a strong focus on sustainable development and conservation. The policy calls for the inclusion of credit-bearing courses and projects related to environmental education, value-based learning, and community service and engagement."

By adding environmental education into the curriculum, promoting sustainability, and encouraging active community involvement at every level of education, NEP 2020 aims to nurture environmentally responsible and globally aware citizens.

Methodology:

This paper is grounded in a review of existing literature. Secondary data has been sourced from journals, articles, books, reports, and reputable websites. The information was collected through a critical analysis of key national and international documents, including the National Education Policy 2020, UGC guidelines and curriculum framework for environmental education, UNESCO's Sustainable Development Goals – particularly Goal 4 – and the broader UNESCO 2030 Agenda .

Conceptual model of environmental literacy:

The conceptual model of Env. Literacy is a comprehensive framework designed to explain the fundamental elements and connections necessary for understanding and interacting with environmental issues. It helps in explaining the various components that influence an individual's ability to make responsible and knowledgeable environmental decisions. The main components used in the conceptual model of environmental literacy are as follows:

1. **Environment Knowledge:** It include the cognitive domain of the individual which help in understanding and gaining the knowledge of the environmental system like ecology, climate system, pollution, biodiversity loss, scientific principles etc.
2. **Environmental skills:** It includes the analysis and critical thinking of the environmental related issues. It also develops problem solving skills and a quest of inquiry and research related to environmental issues.

3. **Values and Attitudes:** A responsible and caring approach for the environment is cultivated, along with an understanding of the ethical aspects of environmental issues and the decision-making processes related to them.
4. **Behavioral Aspects:** Participation in environmental advocacy, policy-making, and community initiatives. Making decisions that reduce one's ecological footprint and promote sustainability is seen in the behavior.
5. **Systems Thinking:** Understanding how different environmental systems are interconnected and how changes in one area can impact others. Engagement and Communication, participation in community-based environmental efforts and initiatives. The conceptual model emphasizes that Environmental literacy goes beyond simply gaining knowledge; it also encompasses the development of skills, attitudes, and behaviors that empower individuals to actively engage with and respond to environmental challenges. It integrates understanding, skills, values, and action related to the environment.

Alignment of NEP2020 with Global Environment Educational Trends:

“This Policy (NEP) 2020 aligns with the global movement for sustainability by promoting the integration of environmental education to all levels of Indian curriculum.” History of environmental literacy starts from early naturalists like Darwin and Muir who raised the awareness about conservation of environment before the 20th century. In 1972 Stockholm Conference created the UN Environment Programme. The World Conservation Strategy and the Brundtland Report’s emphasis on sustainable development, alongside the Tbilisi Declaration and the 1992 Earth Summit's Agenda 21 integrated environmental education into global development plans. In the 2000s, global attention to sustainability was shaped by the “Millennium Development Goals and the UN Decade of Education for Sustainable Development.” This momentum continued with the adoption of the 2015 Sustainable Development Goals, which reinforced the importance of environmental literacy – particularly through Goals 4 (Quality Education) and 13 (Climate Action). Recent trends now emphasize the role of digital technologies, inclusivity, and global cooperation in addressing environmental challenges.

The National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 reflects this global shift toward sustainability and environmental awareness, aligning with the broader historical progression of environmental literacy. The policy strives to cultivate a strong understanding of environmental issues among students, encouraging critical thinking, active citizenship, and a sense of responsibility. In alignment with SD Goals and principles of Tbilisi Declaration, NEP 2020 supports the inclusion of environmental education in teacher training programs. It supports a multidisciplinary, hands-on learning approach to prepare students for meaningful engagement with real-world environmental issues. India’s journey in environmental literacy has evolved from ancient traditions that emphasized living in harmony with nature to a more structured and formal educational approach in recent decades. NEP 2020 builds on this rich heritage by embedding environmental awareness into the core of educational strategies. The 1972 Stockholm Conference marked a significant mark in Indian environment literacy. Initiatives like national awareness campaign and establishment of Ministry of Environment and Forests addressed environmental issues. NEP2020 aims to develop a new generation of environmentally conscious citizens. The National Action Plan on Climate Change and updates to the National Education Policy emphasizes climate change, education and sustainability. Current efforts focus on digital integration, climate education, and addressing environmental justice. India's environmental literacy journey reflects a growing recognition of values of integrating environmental education into policies, curricula, and public knowledgeable efforts. NEP2020’s educational strategies to promote environmental literacy. The Indian National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 promotes environmental literacy through several key strategies:

1. Integration of environmental literacy into the educational curriculum.
2. Values related to sustainability and ethical behavior towards the environment to be inculcated in the citizen.
3. Promoting innovation and research in the field of environmental studies.
4. Collaborating school and community partnership for sustainable practices.

5. Professional development of educators for creating educational resources beneficial for the environment.
6. Includes environmental issues in the curriculum and supports extracurricular activities related to the environment.
7. Encourages student participation in environmental related projects and problem-solving activities.
8. "Utilizes digital technologies to enhance access to environmental education, especially in the far flung and remote areas of the nation."
9. Replacing the rote learning to experimental and environmental friendly learning's.
10. It focuses for converting fragmentation to integration, rigidity to adaptability, prescribed content to learner choice, rote memorization to deep understanding, passive reception to active participation, and exam-centered learning to exploratory inquiry. These strategies aim to integrate environmental literacy into the educational system, fostering a understandable and knowledgeable generation in India according to NEP2020.

Educational strategies of "National Education Policy 2020" at school level:

The National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 of India presents various strategies to promote environmental literacy among school students. Some of these strategies include:

1. Environmental education is to be integrated across curriculum of various subjects and updating course content.
2. Hands-on experiences to be implemented and project-based learning will be provided based on practical experience with environmental issues.
3. Encouraging schools to adopt green practices and eco-friendly infrastructure for having sustainability.
4. Extra curriculum activities to be involved like environmental clubs, competitions and fairs to engage students outside the classroom.
5. Collaborating with local communities and organizations on environmental projects for community based learning.
6. Providing training for the professional development of educators to effectively teach environmental related topics.
7. Empowering students through interactive learning in the environmental processes.
8. Improving and assessing environmental education programs through feedback and evaluation.
9. Awareness about environment, resources, sanitation and hygiene in the schools.

These strategies aim to embed environmental literacy into the school experience, fostering responsible and informed future citizens.

Educational strategies of National Education Policy 2020 at "Higher Education level":

NEP Policy (NEP) 2020 of India at higher education level promotes environmental literacy through:

1. Research in environmental science must be encouraged and establishment of new innovation hubs are to be developed for sustainable solutions.
2. Integrating environmental issues and sustainability across various academic programs and encouraging interdisciplinary studies.
3. Adopting green campus initiatives and eco-friendly infrastructure for preserving ecosystem, natural landscape, reducing carbon emission, conserving the water resources.
4. Collaborating with communities and industries on environmental projects.
5. Learning by doing process by integrating service learning into academic programs.
6. Incorporating environmental topics into teaching and research in the curriculum and by providing training and resources for faculty.
7. Environmental projects led by the students focusing on sustainability are to be encouraged.
8. Online courses and resources on environmental education are to be offered.
9. Developing environmental policies within institutions and assessing their effectiveness.

10. Environmental education is now credit based courses in higher education .UGC classified eight module course as a part of “CBCS (Choice Based Credit System) as an AECC (Ability Enhancement Compulsory Course) for enriching knowledge through content.”
11. Waste reduction and minimizing environmental impact in the life of the people is to be encouraged.
12. Emerging global themes such as the impacts of climate change, strategies for adaptation and mitigation, environmental management, sustainable development, and the conservation and sustainable use of biological resources and biodiversity should be integrated into the curriculum.
13. On 5th June 2024 UGC gave 30 guidelines under the topic “Curriculum Integration in Academics ” for universities which including six themes practical aspect of integrating environmental education like what can be done in courses and programmes, research initiatives, experimental learning, faculty development, institutional policies, campus wide sustainability dashboards. These strategies aim to integrate environmental literacy into higher edu. The N E Policy (NEP) 2020 It outlines educational strategies for Teacher Training Institutions, highlighting that by 2030, a four-year integrated B.Ed. program – offered by multidisciplinary higher education institutions – will become the minimum qualification required for school teachers.

In addition, the NEP focuses on improving environmental literacy at teacher training institutions through:

1. Incorporating environmental education into the curriculum and instructional practices of teacher preparation programs.
2. Offering training and workshops on environmental related issues and teaching strategies.
3. Providing first hands experiences through field trips and collaborations with schools.
4. Creating educational materials and digital tools for effective teaching.
5. Collaborating with communities, NGO’s and industries to expose trainees to real-world environmental practices.
6. Sustainable practices within training institutions are to be done.
7. Engaging students into process and empowering them to the address environmental issues through education.
8. Integrating environment awareness and its conservation and sustainable development in the curriculum.
9. Valuing ongoing research and expert evaluation to improve environmental education.

These strategies aim to prepare future teachers to integrate environmental literacy into their classrooms, foster environment sensitive students.

Suggestions:

To effectively implement environmental education, teachers and administration can utilize a variety of strategies. Here are some practical suggestions:

For Teachers:

1. Integrating environmental issues into subjects like science, social studies, and economics to organize a comprehensive understanding.
2. Use current environmental issues and local case studies to make lessons relevant and engaging.
3. Incorporating field trips, experiments, and outdoor activities to give students real life experiences.
4. Designing projects that address real environmental challenges, such as community clean- ups or sustainability campaigns.
5. Utilize online platforms and apps to enhance environmental education and provide interactive learning experiences.
6. Incorporate games that focus on environmental issues to make learning fun and effective.
7. Encourage learners to engage in discussions & debates on environmental issues to enhance their critical thinking and problem-solving abilities.
8. Analyze case studies of environmental problems and solutions to make students understand about it.
9. Allow students to lead projects on sustainability and environmental literacy.

10. Support the formation of environmental clubs or groups within the educational institution.

Strategies to be used by teachers to enhance the environmental literacy:

1. Attend workshops and seminars focused on environmental education and sustainable teaching practices.
2. Engage with other educators and experts in environmental education to share resources and strategies.
3. Develop and share lesson plans, educational resources, and activities associated with environmental education.
4. Participate in or create networks for sharing best practices and resources regarding environmental education.
5. It is essential to make environmental education a fundamental part of the curriculum, ensuring its alignment with established educational standards.
6. Regularly update curriculum content to reflect the latest environmental science and sustainability practices.

Strategies to be used by administrator to enhance the environmental literacy:

1. Offer financial support for environmental education programs, projects, and research.
2. Partner with local organizations, businesses, and government agencies to strengthen environmental education programs and initiatives.
3. Support policies that promote environmental education and sustainability in the educational institutions.
4. Organize campaigns to promote awareness about the significance of environmental education and sustainability.
5. Organize events such as workshops, seminars and fairs to engage the community and educators in environmental issues. These are some strategies by which a teacher and the administration can effectively promote environmental literacy.

Findings

“N E Policy 2020 and Environmental Education”:

NEP 2020 emphasizes addressing environmental concerns by integrating environmental education into curricula at all the levels that include schools and H. education institutions. It promotes environmental literacy in Indian educational system and also highlights societal issues. Key recommendations of NEP2020 include:

- Merging science and technology with social sciences, humanities, and environmental studies.
- Training professionals in emerging fields like AI (Artificial Intelligence) and 3D machining, focusing on their applications in health, environment, and sustainable living to enhance employability.
- Recognizing disruptive technologies related to clean energy, water conservation, sustainable agriculture, and environmental preservation.

To foster environmental literacy, curricula and textbooks should encompass:

- Environmental attitudes, responsibilities, and ethics.
- Actions that positively impact the environment, such as resource conservation.
- Key environmental concepts, including ecology and ecosystems.
- Sustainability challenges like endangered species, climate change, and global warming.
- Solutions for environmental issues, including recycling and renewable energy.
- The relationship between society, the environment, and technology.

Conclusion

NEP 2020 of India promotes environmental literacy across all educational levels through various strategies. At school level the focus is on encouraging eco friendly behavior, providing hand-on experience and incorporating the environmental education into the curriculum. Higher education emphasis on promoting research, interdisciplinary studies and sustainable campus projects. It will also offer credit based environmental courses. Teacher training institutions included the organizing of

workshops, integrating environmental education into training curricula and real life experiences with the environment. The goals of environmental literacy in NEP2020 for students and future generations focus on equipping individuals with the required knowledge, skills, & values to correlate the challenges related to environment & to promote sustainability. NEP 2020 aligns with the world educational trends. Environmental literacy is a indispensable asset for every individual, as it empowers people to understand, engage and address environmental issues. UN Sustainable Development Goal reinforces environmental literacy. In India NEP2020 is consistent with the environmental literacy strategies at all educational level. This policy will definitely help in making future generations responsible and environmental literate.

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